

Enhancing Debugging Skills With AI-Powered Assistance: A Real-Time Tool for Debugging Support

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1 AI-DEBUGGING ASSISTANT PIPELINE PROMPTS

1.1 LLM SOLUTION GENERATION

The system and main prompts for LLM solution generation are shown in Figure 1.1 and Figure 1.2.

```
You are an assistant helping to fix code to make it pass test.  
  
**Instructions:**  
1. Take the user's code, find a bug and fix it, while keeping the solution as similar to the user's solution as possible.  
2. You don't have to follow the author's solution if it differs from the user's approach, but if it helps fix a bug, you can consider it.  
3. Keep the user's style and as many elements from the user's solution as possible, fixing only the bug that causes the test to fail.  
4. Output only the corrected code, without explanations.
```

Figure 1.1: The system prompt for LLM solution generation.

```
Fix the user code to pass the test, while trying to keep the solution as similar to the original as possible. The solution may consist of several files.  
  
Task Description: <...>  
  
User Solution: <...>  
  
Author Solution: <...>  
  
Failed Test Name: <...>  
  
Failed Test Message: <...>  
  
Provide the answer strictly using the following JSON format: <...>  
  
Avoid adding any unnecessary elements such as triple backticks (e.g., ``` or ```kotlin or ```json). Ensure the response includes the exact filename for each file, as from the user solution.
```

Figure 1.2: The main prompt for LLM solution generation.

1.2 SOLUTION VALIDATION

The system and main prompts for verifying if the solution passes the failed test are shown in Figure 1.3 and Figure 1.4.

```
You are an expert Kotlin code analyst. Your job is to carefully review a solution and determine whether it will pass a specific test case without executing the code. You will be given the following:

A task description that explains what the code is supposed to do.
A test name describing a test scenario.
An expected output from the test.
The solution code written in Kotlin.

Your goals are:
1. To reason through the logic of the solution step-by-step
2. Compare it to the task description and expected test output
3. Decide whether the code will produce the correct result.

YOU MUST NOT RUN THE CODE.

Be meticulous in your analysis and pay attention to edge cases, algorithm logic, and return values.

Conclude your answer with the following format:
1. `PASS` - if the solution is likely to produce the expected output
2. `FAIL` - if there are any issues that would cause it to fail the test.
```

Figure 1.3: The system prompt for verifying if the solution passes the failed test.

```
Help me find out if the solution will pass the test without running it.

# START TASK DESCRIPTION
<...>
# END TASK DESCRIPTION

# Test Name
<...>

# Expected Output
<...>

# Solution Code
<...>

Think step-by-step.
Include the word PASS in your response if you think that solution will pass the test.
Otherwise, include the word FAIL.
```

Figure 1.4: The main prompt for verifying if the solution passes the failed test.

1.3 BREAKPOINTS EXPLANATIONS

The prompt used for generating breakpoint explanations is presented in Figure 1.5.

```
You are the assistant in writing hints to the student on what to look for at each breakpoint. You will be given the code, the lines with final breakpoints indicating the error, and the lines with intermediate breakpoints showing the effect of the incorrect code on the rest of the code. You need to write hints for both kinds of breakpoints.

What to write in the hint?
* Explain what is happening at this point in the code.
* Indicate which variables or objects are changed.

For final breakpoints:
* Explain why the error occurred.

For intermediate breakpoints:
* Emphasise how this relates to the final breakpoint error.

The hint should be small and specific - 1-2 sentences, without unnecessary details.

**Example Output:** <...>

** Your turn **
CODE: <...>
FINAL BREAKPOINTS: <...>
INTERMEDIATE BREAKPOINTS: <...>

Output the final result as a JSON object, ensuring no additional logic is included.
```

Figure 1.5: The prompt for generating breakpoint explanations.

2 USABILITY STUDY

2.1 INTERVIEW SCRIPT

Hello, ___! Thank you for joining me today. I'm [NAME], a Researcher here at [HIDDEN NAME]. Today, we are here to study **your experience with our newly prototyped AI Debugger**. This system is intended to support novice programmers while learning how to debug, so it has an educational purpose so to speak.

Have you ever participated in a prototype testing? For such sessions, we usually have coding tasks that we ask participants to solve with the help of the prototype. The prototype **does not have the full functionality** of IDE but is working as a proxy of our idea. So please, be aware that some fields or buttons might be inactive.

Overall, we are genuinely interested in your experience with it and would like to hear your feedback, both negative and positive. All would be helpful for us to refine the prototype. So please, **feel free to share anything and everything**.

Also, I would like to ask your permission to **record** this session. We keep all recordings confidential, make anonymized summaries out of them, and delete everything once the research is over so that no personal data will be used. Is that OK with you?

Now let me start the recording, and when it starts, I will ask for your permission to record this session once again. [START RECORDING]

[REPEAT] I would like to have your permission to record this session.

Great! All technical nuances we dealt with. Before we start the main part, could you please tell me **a bit about yourself?** Where are you studying now, what is your major?

Amazing! Thanks for sharing! Do you have any questions for me at this point? If not, let's start with the prototype.

Here is the **link** to the task [LINK], please, open it and share your screen.

Please take a look at the code. A student wrote a price management program for an electronics store. There is a function for applying a discount on an item, and a function for applying tax. You can read more details about the taxing and discounting rules in the task description on your screen. This code contains a bug. Do you see it right away? No worries if not – it is intended! But we need to check.

- **if yes:**

Amazing! What bug do you see here?

Great! Let's see if the system would align with your way of thinking about that.

- **if no:**

Super! Let's see if the system would be of use to you to find this bug eventually.

Let's check the code. Yep, as you see, there is a bug in this code. Please start a debugging session to resolve it.

By clicking anywhere on the screen, you can see which buttons are actionable. You can also place your own breakpoints in addition to the ones suggested by the assistant. You do not need to edit the code, you only need to find out what the mistake is.

As you use the prototype, just speak out loud about what you're doing and thinking. Let me know what you're trying to do, what you notice, and if anything is confusing or unexpected. If you pause or feel unsure about something, tell me about that too. Let's try now. Please, describe what you see before you.

Great, please, proceed in the same vein. Ultimately, your task is to go through the debugging cycle to understand and tell me where the bug is and how to change the code to fix it.

...

Now that the debug cycle is finished, could you please describe what the bug was and how we might fix it?

- **if incorrect:**

Oh, interesting idea! But there is another answer as well. Let's go through the cycle once again and see if you'll find another solution for this bug. Don't let it discourage you; your idea is great as well. We just want to see if the system helps you see some other solution here.

Imagine you're running a small electronics store, and you need a program to help you manage item prices.

Implement two functions: **applyTax** that increases the item's price by a given tax percentage, and **applyDiscount** that reduces the price by a given discount percentage.

Then, recreate the following scenario using the implemented functions.

Imagine a customer wants to purchase two laptops: one brand-new and one with cosmetic damage. The original laptop is priced at **1000\$**. You decide to offer a **10%** discount on the damaged laptop. After the discount is applied, you must also account for a **5%** tax on the discounted price. For the undamaged laptop, you apply a **20%** tax directly to its full price. Calculate and display the combined price of the customer's purchase.

Figure 2.1: A programming task for the interview.

- **if correct:**

Great, your answer is correct! Thank you! Now, let me ask you about your experience during the session.

1. How did you feel overall when using the prototype?
2. How easy was it for you to figure out how to use this feature?
3. How much time do you think it would take to find and understand this bug without the prototype, compared to using it?
4. What did you like about debugging using this prototype?
5. What did you not like about debugging using this prototype?
6. How different was suggested by the prototype workflow from your typical "style" of debugging?
7. How do you usually start a debug session, in what part of a program do you put your first breakpoint?
8. How would you change this prototype to make it more convenient for you?
9. Did you notice that there were some hints for the breakpoints? What did they do for you in your opinion? Would you change the content of the hints in any way?
10. Did you notice different colors of breakpoints? Why were they different in your opinion?
11. In your opinion, to what extent does this assistant help in learning how to debug?
12. How likely are you to use such a feature on a scale from 0 to 10?
13. On a scale from 0 to 10, how likely are you to recommend this feature to your peers?

Thank you very much for all your answers. Do you have anything to add to our conversation? Would you like to ask me something?

[SAY GOODBYE] [STOP THE RECORDING]

2.2 INTERVIEW TASK

The given programming task is presented in Figure 2.1. Interview participants worked with an interactive Figma prototype with limited functionality, for instance, they are not able to edit code. Participants are provided with a solution with **one bug**. Their task is to *identify* and *explain the bug* in the provided solution, suggesting *how it could be fixed* in the code. The source code of the solution containing the bug, as well as the explanation for the bug, are shown in Figure 2.2.

Description of the bug. Because the code copies only the *reference* instead of the actual object (line 10), `originalItem` and `discountedItem` end up pointing to the same instance. As a result, any modifications applied to the discounted item also affect the original item, which leads to an incorrect final total.

Possible ways to fix the bug. Figure 2.3 describes possible bug fixes in `applyDiscount` function. Figure 2.4 describes possible bug fixes in `main` function.

```

1  data class Item(var name: String, var price: Double)
2
3  fun applyTax(item: Item, taxRate: Double): Item {
4      val taxAmount = item.price * taxRate / 100
5      item.price += taxAmount
6      return item
7  }
8
9  fun applyDiscount(item: Item, discount: Double): Item {
10     val discountedItem = item
11     discountedItem.price -= discountedItem.price * discount / 100
12     return discountedItem
13 }
14
15 fun main() {
16     val originalItem = Item("Laptop", 1000.0)
17     val discountedItem = applyDiscount(originalItem, 10.0)
18
19     applyTax(discountedItem, 5.0)
20     applyTax(originalItem, 20.0)
21
22     println(originalItem.price + discountedItem.price)
23 }

```

Figure 2.2: Pre-written buggy solution for the provided programming task.

a

```

10 fun applyDiscount(item: Item, discount: Double): Item {
11     val discountedItem = item.copy()
12     discountedItem.price -= discountedItem.price * discount / 100
13     return discountedItem
14 }

```

b

```

10 fun applyDiscount(item: Item, discount: Double): Item {
11     val discountedItem = item
12     newPrice = item.price - (item.price * discount / 100)
13     return Item(item.name, newPrice)
14 }

```

c

```

1  data class Item(var name: String, var price: Double) {
2      fun deepCopy() = Item(name, price)
3  }

```

```

10 fun applyDiscount(item: Item, discount: Double): Item {
11     val discountedItem = item.deepCopy()
12     discountedItem.price -= discountedItem.price * discount / 100
13     return discountedItem
14 }

```

Figure 2.3: Possible bug fixes in applyDiscount function: a) Clone the Item in applyDiscount; b) Create a new Item explicitly; c) Introduce a deep copy constructor or method for Item and use it in applyDiscount.

3 CLASSROOM STUDY

3.1 PRE-TEST PHASE TASK

The given programming task is to implement a *console-based Hangman game* in Kotlin. Here is a brief description of the game's concept:

- *Secret Word*: The program picks a random word from a predefined list.
- *Hidden Display*: The word is shown as underscores separated by spaces (e.g., `_____` for a four-letter word).

```

a 15 fun main() {
    16 val originalItem = Item("Laptop", 1000.0)
    17 val discountedItem = applyDiscount(originalItem.copy(), 10.0)
    18
    19 applyTax(discountedItem, 5.0)
    20 applyTax(originalItem, 20.0)
    21
    22 println(originalItem.price + discountedItem.price)
    23 }

b 15 fun main() {
    16 val originalItem = Item("Laptop", 1000.0)
    17 val discountedItem = originalItem.copy()
    18 applyDiscount(originalItem, 10.0)
    19
    20 applyTax(discountedItem, 5.0)
    21 applyTax(originalItem, 20.0)
    22
    23 println(originalItem.price + discountedItem.price)
    24 }

```

Figure 2.4: Possible bug fixes in main function: a) Pass a copied Item to applyDiscount in main; b) Manually create a copy before passing to applyDiscount.

- *Player Guess*: Each turn, the player enters a single letter:
 - If the letter is in the secret word, all matching positions become visible.
 - If not, the player loses one attempt.
- *End Conditions*:
 - *Win*: All letters revealed before running out of attempts.
 - *Lose*: Attempts reach zero before the word is fully guessed.

Study participants receive a complete source file of the solution with **two bugs**. Their task is to *identify* and *fix the bugs* in the provided solution. The bugs presented in this task are shown and explained in Listing 1 and Listing 2.

```

fun generateNewUserWord(secret: String, guess: Char, currentUserWord: String): String {
    val firstMatchIndex = secret.indexOf(guess)
    val condensed = currentUserWord.filter { !it.isWhitespace() }
    return condensed.mapIndexed { i, c ->
        // if (i == firstMatchIndex) guess else c
        if (secret[i] == guess) guess else c
    }.joinToString(" ")
}

```

Listing 1: First bug in the pre-test phase task. The generateNewUserWord function is intended to update the hidden word by revealing all positions of the guessed letter. However, the buggy implementation only checks the first matching index, so only one occurrence is revealed instead of all of them.

```

fun safeUserInput(): Char {
    var guess: String
    do {
        println("Please input your guess.")
        guess = safeReadLine()
    } while (!isCorrectInput(guess))
    return guess[0].lowercaseChar().uppercaseChar()
}

```

Listing 2: Second bug in the pre-test phase task. The safeUserInput function is intended to repeatedly prompt the user until a valid single-letter input is provided, and then return it in uppercase. However, the buggy implementation converts the character to lowercase.

3.2 INTERVENTION PHASE TASKS

In this phase, study participants are given a series of programming tasks to build a single-file project in Kotlin step by step. The goal of this project is to create a simple *Photoshop console app* that can apply different filters to character images. Here are the steps students are asked to complete:

1. Implement the `trimPicture` function, which accepts a picture and *removes all indents* from it.
2. Implement the `applyFilter` function. It accepts a picture and a filter name, applies the `trimPicture` function to the picture, then *applies the specified filter*, and finally returns the updated picture. To apply a filter, students should call one of the already defined functions: `applyBordersFilter` or `applySquaredFilter`.
3. Implement the `applyBordersFilter` function, which takes a single string argument, picture, and returns a new picture with a *borders filter applied*.
4. Implement the `applySquaredFilter` function, which also takes a single string argument, picture, and returns a new picture with a *squared filter applied*.
5. Implement the `safeReadLine` function, which *returns* the string input by the user *or throws an error* if a null value was received.
6. Implement the `choosePicture` function that *allows choosing a predefined picture* by its name.
7. Implement the `getPicture` function, which *asks the user to choose* a predefined picture *or to input* a custom picture.
8. Implement the `photoshop` function, which *combines* all functions together.

To complete the given tasks, study participants are introduced to the following theory topics: multi-row strings, when expressions, basic handling of errors, string builder, and null safety.

3.3 POST-TEST PHASE TASK

The given programming task is to implement a *console application* that creates a rectangular “canvas” by tiling a small text pattern in Kotlin. The pattern can be predefined or custom, and the user can choose between two generator types: `canvas` or `canvasGaps`. Here is the application workflow:

- The program starts by asking the user:
Do you want to use a predefined pattern or a custom one?
Please input 'yes' for a predefined pattern or 'no' for a custom one.
- Based on the user's answer:
 - If they choose a *custom pattern*, they type it in themselves.
 - If they choose a *predefined pattern*, they select one from a list.
- Next, the user chooses a *generator type*:
 - `canvas` – Repeats the pattern regularly.
 - `canvasGaps` – Adds empty gaps between repeated patterns.
- Finally, the user sets the *width* and *height* for the generated image.
- The program generates the canvas according to the chosen settings and displays it in the console.

Study participants receive a complete source file of the solution with **two bugs**. Their task is to *identify* and *fix the bugs* in the provided solution. The bugs presented in this task are shown and explained in Listing 3 and Listing 4.

```

fun dropTopLine(image: String, width: Int, patternHeight: Int, patternWidth: Int): String {
    if (patternHeight <= 1) return image
    return image.dropWhile { it != '\n' }.drop(1)
}

```

Listing 3: First bug in the post-test phase task. The `dropTopLine` function is intended to create a cascading effect by removing the first line of the given pattern. However, the `dropWhile` function stops before the newline character but does not remove it, resulting in a leading '\n' on each call.

```

fun repeatHorizontallyWithGaps(pattern: String, n: Int, patternWidth: Int, gapFirst: Boolean): String {
    val gap = separator.toString().repeat(patternWidth)
    return pattern.lines().joinToString(newLineSymbol) {
        val patLine = fillPatternRow(it, patternWidth)
        if (gapFirst) {
            (gap + patLine).repeat(n / 2) + gap.repeat(n % 2)
        } else {
            (patLine + gap).repeat(n / 2) + gap.patLine.repeat(n % 2)
        }
    }
}

```

Listing 4: Second bug in the post-test phase task. The `repeatHorizontallyWithGaps` function is intended to repeat a pattern horizontally with gaps between repetitions. However, when `gapFirst = false` and the number of repetitions is odd, the last pattern is omitted and replaced by a trailing gap.